

'CANDIDATUS LIBERIBACTER SOLANACEARUM', DETECTED ON CARROT AND TOMATO IN TUNISIA

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In 2014, 2015 and 2016 symptoms associated in several countries to '*Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*' (CaLsol) were observed on carrot and tomato plants in Kairouan region, Tunisia. Yield losses and vegetative disorders were observed in affected fields. Samples were analysed by real-time PCR to investigate if such bacterium and/or to phytoplasmas and/or to *Spiroplasma citri* were detected. Carrot and tomato plants of local Tunisian cultivars, insect vectors and weeds were analyzed, with positive results for CaLsol in 14 out of 93 samples of carrots plants and 2 out of 87 samples of tomato plants. On the contrary 57 insect vectors were negative for CaLsol (49 *Bactericera trigonica* and 8 *B. nigricornis*) and also six samples from *Morella* sp. The obtained results showed the detection of CaLsol and the absence of phytoplasmas and *S. citri* in all samples. Furthermore, Tunisian carrot seeds of local production were also analyzed and were positive for CaLsol, with average cell viability around 55%, much higher than that of commercial European seeds (3-5%). Probably this big difference is related to the lack of treatments in Tunisian seeds. The haplotype of CaLsol present in positive carrot plants was analyzed and characterized as E and D, but interestingly, the haplotype D was also detected in the three lots of Tunisian carrot seeds. CaLsol haplotype of tomato plants is pending. This is the first report of the presence of CaLsol in Tunisia and the first in tomato outside America and New Zealand.